

Kruunuvooren silta (Crown Bridge) steel structures **Project execution with focus on the bridges steel structures**

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ABSTRACT

Kruunuvooren silta (Crown Bridge) is one of the biggest bridge projects executed in the history of Nordec. The bridge will also be the longest bridge in Finland when completed. The bridge is 1,2 km long and the bridge deck is 15,3 m wide. The bridge is a cable stayed bridge with a 135 m high pylon in the centre with a span of 260 m on each side of the pylon. The bridge has a vertical clearance of 20 metres and the steel superstructure has a total weight of 6300 tons. The bridge is designed to last for 200 years and designed for Helsinki light rail traffic and pedestrians.

Nordec's scope includes manufacturing, installation, and surface treatment of the steel structures (superstructure and pylon cable anchor boxes). Erection engineering and planning all launches and lifts is also included in Nordec's scope.

All plates of the main girders are made of steel quality S460 ML and were manufactured in Nordec's factory in Ylivieska. All components of the superstructure were assembled and welded together on site. The two 260-meter spans were assembled off site into eight bigger sections of 50-72,5 meters and weight of appr. 500 tons per section. These were lifted into final position on temporary supports with the crane-ship "Uglen". The approach bridges were launched into final position with hydraulic jacks and sliding bearings.

The geometry of the superstructures was ensured by phase-modelling the bridge according to its actual position and load on the bridge deck (form, rebar etc.) during installation. The pre-assembled "cable-sections" of the 260-meter spans were also modelled separately to enable installation with high accuracy at the pre-assembly area.

Progress and status (POC) was reported in real time using Trimble connect.

Keywords: Incremental Launching, Crane-vessel Installation, Staged Construction Analysis

1 INTRODUCTION

This introduction chapter will give the reader some general information about the project and the structure of this article. As the article is written for the Nordic Steel Conference 2024, the focus in the article will be on the bridge steel structures, covering a spectrum starting from design to execution and installation on site. The article includes six main chapters where different areas are being covered. The first chapter provides the reader with a short introduction of the project, its stakeholders, and some brief technical facts about the bridge structure. The following chapters cover the most essential parts in the construction process such as *Design*, *Execution pre-planning*, *Manufacturing*, and *Installation*. The last chapter of the article is a summary of the content in the article and acknowledgment to parties that have been involved shaping the article.

1.1 General facts about the project

The Crown Bridge is the biggest bridge constructed in the project “The Crown Bridges Light Rail” that is carried out by the city of Helsinki. The new light rail route will connect Laajasalo, Korkeasaari and Kalasatama to Hakaniemi in 2027. It will also provide a new seaside route for cyclists and pedestrians.

Construction works started in the autumn of 2021 and is still on-going when this article is being written. The primary objective of the Crown Bridges project is to provide a quick and reliable transport connection from the growing Laajasalo area to the centre of the city. The Crown Bridges light rail connection will ensure smooth traffic both inside and in and out of Laajasalo during a period which will see the area’s population more than double thanks to the completion of a wholly new residential district, Kruunuvuorenranta, and considerable infill development. The project will also enable significantly improved transport connections to and from Korkeasaari. A direct light rail connection between the city centre and Laajasalo will also decrease the congestion projected for the eastern branches of the metro system. (1)

In addition to the light rail connection, the Crown Bridges project will also make the Kalasatama, Korkeasaari, Mustikkamaa and Laajasalo areas accessible by bicycle or on foot, as the light rail line will be bordered by a high-quality bicycle route/walkway. Thanks to the project, the shortest way from Kruunuvuorenranta to the Central Railway Station, which is currently 11 km and runs via Itäväylä, will decrease to just 5.5 km. The City of Helsinki aims to increase sustainable transport’s share of all passenger traffic. The Crown Brides project will promote sustainable transport by creating new routes for walkers, bicyclists and public transport. This will increase their combined share of all traffic moving inside the city. The main contractor is a joint venture including the companies YIT Oy and Kreate Oy. (2)

1.2 Technical facts about the bridge

The new Kruunuvuori Bridge connecting Korkeasaari and Kruunuvuorenranta is to become the longest, tallest and longest-standing bridge in Finland, and it is also globally exceptional as bridges of this size have not been built for the sole use of public transport, pedestrian traffic and cycling. The bridge thus becomes an interesting attraction not only due to its size, but also due to the advanced traffic thinking behind its design. (3)

Fig. 1. Kruunuvuori Bridge, view from Kulosaari. (Picture: WSP, Knight Architects)

The bridge is a cable stayed bridge with a centre pylon that rises to a height of 135 metres and can be seen from far away at any time of the day. The bridge's vertical clearance at the main boat channel is 20 metres, and the width of the bridge deck varies from 15,3 meters to 19,3 meters. The total length of the bridge superstructure is 1193 meters and bridge total length will be 1228 meters when completed.

The bridge is designed for a service life of 200 years. Some structures are intended to be renewed, but structures that requires a 200-year service life include hard-to-repair load-bearing structures such as pylons, intermediate supports, and deck steel beams. For steel structures, durability is sought through design solutions: careful planning and implementation of details avoids structural solutions that would cause steel fatigue, for example.

1.3 Nordec and the Steel Contractor Scope

Nordec Oy was chosen as steel contractor in this project. Nordec is a Finland based company which is operating within the steel construction industry. The company has its roots from the Finnish company Rautaruukki, which was founded by the Finnish government in the 1960's, to ensure raw material for the Finnish shipyard and metal industry. (4)

Nordec Group Corporation is, from year 2022, owned by a new consortium company where the two major shareholders are Harjavalta Oy and Tirinom Oy. (5)

The Nordec's scope of works included execution of all steel beams of the superstructure and the anchor boxes on the top of the pylon. All structures together make up a total mass of 6300 tons of steel structures. The scope included manufacturing of the steel beams at Nordec's factory in Ylivieska, including surface treatment and transport to the construction site. On the construction site Nordec's scope included pre-assembly, installation, welding and surface treatment of all steel structures. Erection engineering and site planning was also included in Nordec's scope together with all major lifting and jacking operations.

2 BRIDGE STEEL DESIGN

The basic solution for the bridge was designed by WSP and Ramboll handled the construction design and engineering.

The planning of the Kruunuvuori Bridge was launched in 2012 with an international design competition, the aim of which was to design a transport link from Nihti to Kruunuvuorenranta, via the island of Korkeasaari. The focus was on the design of the Kruunuvuori Bridge, which forms a crossing point between Palosaari and Kruunuvuori. Out of 52 entries, 10 proposals were accepted, including that of WSP's international design group Gemma Regalis was selected as the winner.

The design of the bridge took the user's perspective very much into account, both in terms of visual appearance and user-friendliness. The aim was to make the bridge, which is over one kilometre long, light and airy, to minimize the disruptive effect on the landscape. The bridge horizontal curvature is based not only on structural reasons, but also on improving the user experience - by walking on a curved bridge, a person can better perceive the destination. The functionality and interior details of the bridge have been carefully considered to meet the needs of pedestrians, cyclists, and public transport users.

The total length of the Kruunuvuori Bridge deck is over one kilometre long and the bridge superstructure is continuous between the ground supports. In the middle of the horizontal arched

bridge is a sloping rope section formed by a pylon and two main sections of 260-metre. The main bridge combines two access bridges, which are continuous composite beam bridges.

A life span of 200 years has been set for the Kruunuvuori Bridge. The uniquely long-life calls into question the structural design and material choices, and also creates special requirements for bridge maintenance. A significant part of the design was to identify structures and components that are highly stressed and cannot be replaced. The long service life places particular demands on the design of the bridge's supporting structures, i.e. steel and concrete structures.

The durability of the bridge steel structures is ensured by careful planning and implementation to avoid possible fatigue of the steel structures. Fatigue of steel structures can be observed in long-term use, especially in joints and stiffeners. The emphasis is therefore in finding the simplest and most functional solutions possible in the design. (6)

Ramboll is delivering the construction design and engineering for the bridge. "Every time a tram passes over the bridge, a fatigue cycle that affects the resistance of the steel occurs, but this bridge will last 200 years. It is twice as long as the usual 100," says Ilkka Ojala, Chief Designer from Ramboll. Long service life in the quality and durability properties of the concrete is also considered. "Much attention is paid to details. If a component cannot last 200 years, it will be replaced", Ilkka continues. The concrete deck of the bridge rests on large steel girders with spans the maximum length of 260 metres. The maximum height for boats going under the bridge is 20 metres. The whole structure will require about 6 million kilograms of steel. Originally, the deck structure of the bridge was to be installed at the main openings supported by diagonal cables using the cantilever method. However, the construction schedule was accelerated by installing the deck in large blocks. Due to the change in construction method, all steel structures on the deck will be re-dimensioned. Innovative data modelling process shortens design time. Due to the tight schedule, design automation has been enhanced, while a parametric workflow enables the design and data modelling processes to occur simultaneously. Algorithms were used to create dependencies between different components, allowing automatic updates of changes throughout the model. "Our approach is similar to programming. The entire geometry of the bridge is encoded, making it easy to change data on the fly as the plans are refined," says Ojala. (7)

3 EXECUTION PRE-PLANNING

Around five years ago first plans on how to execute the project were made. The biggest decisions were made during this time as method for installing all steel structures were proposed, and with that the total time of construction could be estimated more exactly. Nordec's proposal included **incremental launching** of the approach bridges on each shore, and the bridge sections that form the longest spans on 260 meters were **installed with a crane-vessel**. The pylons anchor-boxes are installed by using a tower crane.

This proposal of installation method would have a huge impact on the total construction time of the project, as the original proposal for method of installation was installation by using the cantilever-method, which requires the pylon to be completed before the bridge sections of the two main spans can be erected.

3.1 Execution plan for installation

This chapter will provide the reader with a brief insight on the most essential parts of the pre-planning and preparation work the installation and construction work required. As usually in construction projects, construction time schedules are set tight, which requires meticulous pre-

planning to get all the different processes and activities to work together throughout the whole project. The most essential parts, regarding execution of the steel structures, will be presented in the sub-chapters below.

3.1.1 *Methods of installation (Erection Engineering)*

As mentioned above, Nordec's two main methods of installation included incremental launching and crane-vessel installation. The two different methods require specific pre-planning and will be explained more in detail below.

The part of the bridge structures located at the supports, the approach bridges, were installed by **incremental launching** with hydraulic jacks. This means that the bridge structure is pre-assembled behind the abutment on each shore, and then pushed (launched) out on the supports. After each launch the structure is pro-longed with a length of one span.

This method requires that the jacks, that are pushing the structures out on the supports, are properly connected and supported by a solid foundation at the abutment. The abutment had to be designed to withstand the horizontal load created by the launch. This means a maximum limit for the total combined load must be set based on the capacity of the launching equipment and a reasonable size and dimension of the abutment. Usually, the load limit is set by adding the weight of the formwork to the self-weight of the steel structures, which was also the case here.

Incremental launching also set requirements on the pre-assembly area that must be big enough to fit all the bridge structures of each phase behind the abutment.

Incremental launching also determines the maximum size of steel beams and components that can be assembled on site, which also goes hand-in-hand with the limits of the factory regarding size and weight.

Fig. 2. Launching equipment at the eastern abutment (Picture: Nordec Oy)

The other main method of installation was **crane-vessel installation** with a crane-ship of the bridge sections of the two main spans, the stay-cable area. This method was chosen because of the beneficial pre-conditions the area offered when it comes to sea depth, waves, and general weather conditions. The bridge site is located in a considerably calm location protected by the inner archipelago from bigger waves and hard winds. The shallow water also enables the construction of temporary supports

and bridges for site traffic. Being able to build temporary supports cost-efficiently made the idea of crane-vessel installation possible.

Crane-vessel installation requires a lot of pre-planning and set some requirement on the pre-conditions on the seabed, coastlines, water depth, weather conditions, pick-up points, other marine traffic in the area and much more.

Fig. 3. Installation with crane-vessel. (Picture: Nordec Oy)

The whole seabed of the area where the vessel was going to operate was scanned in order to get bathymetric data to be able to plan eventual need for excavation.

The maximum size of the bridge sections to be lifted were also based on the lifting capacity of the crane-vessel. The cable-sections had to be designed to withstand the load and stress the lift transfers to the structures. This required meticulous planning of lifting points, additional stiffeners and supports, locking and connecting points, anchoring, and steering and guiding structures etc.

Another essential part in the erection engineering process is analysing the of centre of gravity and positioning of lifting lugs.

3.1.2 Temporary support structures

An essential part of the pre-planning phase includes designing all temporary structures so they can serve all phases of the construction. Nordec's scope included temporary structure for launching operations, whereas other temporary support structures such as the access-bridge and support towers were executed by the main contractor. However, all parties were involved in the pre-planning to ensure that the temporary structures would serve all operations carried out by each contractor.

The **temporary structures required for launching** include support structures at the abutments, *sliding bearings* on the pre-assembly area and the *nose* in front of the bridge deck. These are all designed to withstand the heavy load from the bridge deck and to ensure a smooth controlled launch. As the bridge deck has an s-curve at the eastern shore, the support structures had to be designed so that their location can be adjusted during the launch as the whole bridge deck moves sideways on the same time it is pushed forward. Locking the bridge deck to the abutments after each launch had also to be

planned properly as the bridge after each launch stand on a slippery surface and downhill with an 2,5° incline.

The **support towers** were built to enable crane-vessel installation of the cable-sections. The number of towers and their size were designed based on the size and weight of the cable-sections. The towers will not solely take the load from the steel structures but do also have to carry the load of the concrete deck and withstand the load from equipment and material for following construction phases such as cable installation. The total number of support towers is 10 and they have a combined steel mass of 1000 tons. Towers are made from leftover piles of 813/18 and 700/14.2 which can be reused in future projects. The height of support towers varies between 25 and 42 meters. Outermost towers are anchored to bedrock to withstand wind loads during cable installations. (8)

3.2 Execution plan workshop

As mentioned earlier pre-planning of installation of the steel structures goes hand in hand with pre-planning with the factory, as the factory have some limits when it comes to the size and weight of the steel beams. The load capacity and ability to produce and deliver the right number of elements needed on time to the site must also be considered during the pre-planning phase. Material availability and delivery times do also play an important role in the manufacturing process and needs to be planned properly.

3.2.1 Bridge structures compatibility with workshop

Nordec's factory have some limits when it comes to the size of elements produced. These must be taken into consideration when designing the different elements and making workshop drawings. Nordec's factory in Ylivieska can produce beams up to 33 m long with a maximum weight of 95 tons. The weight limit is also determined based on the limits set by transportation as most of the elements are transported to site on normal main roads. All these aspects must be considered in a early phase of the project.

3.2.2 Material sourcing

Through great cooperation we were able to secure the materials in good time before the execution. The projects initial data was provided at an early stage, which enabled us to study and map the different suppliers by plate quality (S460ML), particularly large plate size (max 24 tons) and plate thickness up to 80mm.

Due to the supplier's production limitations and the projects time schedule, we decided to divide the plate purchasing between two European suppliers. This way we were able to secure the delivery of materials at the right time. This was crucial for manufacturing plant in Ylivieska.

The sourcing in this project also had a bit of luck. The price was locked to MEPS and the capacity was booked before the Russian attack on Ukraine. After which the prizes changed dramatically as well as the availability of materials. This caused big problems for a lot of companies during this time.

Some interesting numbers:

Steel amount in superstructure	6 500 tons
Welding wire for superstructure	50 tons
Studs in superstructure	140 000 pcs

4 MANUFACTURING

The steel structures were manufactured at Nordec's factory in Ylivieska, Finland. The factory operations were started in 1977. The production facilities have a floor area of 14 000 m², and an annual production capacity of 13 000 tons per year. The factory has 125 employees, and the factory has produced more than 1000 bridges through the years, delivered worldwide.

Nordec's competitive edge is welded beams as one of the most sophisticated welding lines in Europe can be found in the Ylivieska factory. The welding line is capable to fabricate welded beams up to 4,2 m high and 1,4 m wide. The factory premises also comprises an own paint shop, a CNC operated drilling line, automated flame cutting as well as automated grinding of flame cut surfaces and corners. The factory also has a train rail on the premises that is connected to the Finnish railway system, that enables train transport directly into our factory.

The material used in this project, in both flanges and webs in all main- and cross beams is 460ML. Only outfitting parts are made of S355. This is not common for bridge I-beams.

In Finland it is common to use multiple plates on top of each other to create a thicker flange. In the Kruunuvuori bridge, the thickest flange was 80mm + 80mm + 60mm = 220mm. This means that when joining these types of beams, the amount of work is multiplied, since there will be two additional welds per plate. So, in this case one weld becomes five welds. This also applies when cross girders are placed in locations with multiple plates for the flanges. To compensate for this, plates as large as possible (25t) was purchased to minimize the amount of welding.

The workshop load planning is crucial in these types of large projects. Multiple things must be considered. Things like workshop load, paint shop load, shipment scheduling and of course with these amounts of materials, the storage at the factory is a challenge. Both with the plates and the completed products. In addition to this, the material must be available in time, and the product must be ready in time for delivery to the construction site.

The geometrical tolerances in this project, especially for the stay cable anchor points, are very small (EXC4). When you combine this with thick materials and large welds, there is a risk for deformations. The welding methods for these welds needs to be very well planned, and small adjustments needs to be done to the welding methods to compensate for material shrinking, and heat impact on geometry.

In this project the digital work environment has played a significant role. Status and POC reporting have been done through Trimble Connect. There has been an updated workshop 3D model available in Tekla at all times. We have also increased the use of optical 3D measuring tools (3D-model + Tachymeter) in the workshop when manufacturing this bridge. This is crucial in order to achieve the right geometrical shape, especially for the complicated stay cable anchor boxes in the top of the pylon.

5 INSTALLATION

This chapter will cover the most essential parts of the installation of the steel structures. The chapter includes five sub-chapters where each part is briefly described.

5.1 Pre-assembly of superstructure sections

All steel structures for the bridge were transported from Ylivieska factory to the construction site using normal road transport. The heaviest beam transported had a weight of 85 tons, and the longest beams

were 33 meters. The components of the superstructure (main beams, cross beams, cable-anchors, and inspection bridge) were pre-assembled on a pre-assembly area located at, or near the construction site. The bridge sections for the approach bridges were assembled behind the abutment on each shore. The number of sections to be installed varied depending on how many section that were to be launched in each phase. One phase typically included installation of 2-3 sections. The cable-sections that were installed with the crane-vessel were pre-assembled into six 50 meters long section and two 72,5 meters long sections and were installed on a separate area located at coastline in Sompasaari, where the crane vessel was able to pick up the cable-section and transport them to the bridge site.

Fig. 4. Pre-assembled cable sections at Sompasaari. (Picture: Nordec Oy)

After all components were installed for each phase, all components were welded together according to welding class B (EXC3-structures) and B90 (EXC4-structures). After that, NDT-testing was done to ensure the quality of the welds. When all welds had been tested and approved all welding joints were painted according to painting system C-5M(H).

As the bridge is designed to last for 200 years, quality requirements were high. To ensure that the right quality level was reached, all welding works and surface treatment was done in a controlled climate inside temporary weather protection tents with heating. This way all works could be done when protected from wind and rain and freezing winter conditions.

5.2 Incremental launching

The launching was in several phases, where the length of each launch was typically 63 meters. The equipment used was hydraulic hollow cylinder jacks, with strand-wires connected to the jacks and the back of the bridge. When the jacks are activated, the bridge moves in the same pace and length as one stroke, approximately 10 meters per hour. The launches were monitored from the jacking equipment located next to the abutment.

5.3 Installation with crane vessel

The biggest phase during the whole project was the installation of the cable sections with the crane-vessel. The lifting operation had to be planned in detail to avoid any possible disturbances during the time for the lifts. The time window in which the lifting operation was possible to execute was also short as the whole operation is totally dependent on the weather conditions, and the date for the lifts

and the vessel must be booked one year in advance. An old harbour area located nearby was used as pre-assembly area for the cable-sections. The pre-assembly area at the old harbour was optimal for the project as it was located within one kilometre distance from the bridge site, with enough water depth and access to the coastline and with ready anchor points for the vessel to park at shore, and to pick-up the big cable-sections. The sections were picked up at three different pick-up points around Sompasaari, and then transported to the bridge site. As there were only three pick-up points, five sections had to be transported to the pick-up points with a multi-wheeler (SPMT). The maximum weight the crane vessel could lift was 500 tons. Due to the weight limitations, two section were installed without formwork installed. All eight sections were installed in six days.

5.4 Geometry assurance

To facilitate geometry control and ensuring the shape of the superstructure, an extended use of digital tools was implemented. All structures were installed according to tailor-made models for each bridge section. The process behind the modelling is described more detailed in the sub-chapters below.

5.4.1 Staged Construction analysis

In the client's design, the final geometry of the bridge, planned for the time of opening, serves as the baseline. However, to calculate the geometry required for component fabrication and various stages of segment installation during bridge construction, a staged construction analysis is needed. This analysis systematically simulates the entire construction process, adhering to the planned schedule. Each stage influencing the structure's geometry is included in the analysis. These stages encompass the addition of new structural members (resulting in a change of the structural system), introduction of loads, and alterations in material properties over time, such as creep and shrinkage.

To ensure precision, a geometrically accurate model was prepared. The model's geometry aligns with the coordinate system used on the construction site, eliminating the need for coordinate translations. This approach facilitates the direct use of results from the on-site model with minimal post-processing. The widely used FEM software, SOFiSTiK 2022, was employed for the analysis. It features the capability to export the deformed model geometry in IFC format at any stage of the analysis, subsequently utilized for geometry control surveys on-site.

The analysis was executed iteratively, aiming to achieve the planned geometry at the time of opening. After each construction cycle, a new initial geometry was employed. Iterations concluded upon achieving the targeted system geometry. Cable forces were included as iteration variables to align them with the designed forces. The forward analysis method was utilized to accurately account for nonlinear effects such as cable sag, creep, and shrinkage.

The result of the analysis provides the geometry of each structural component at every active construction stage. The geometry of each component is determined first time just prior to the activation of its dead load. This stage defines the fabrication shape of steel components (essential for shop drawings) or the formwork shape prior to concreting. As the analysis spans all construction stages, culminating in the planned geometry, it provides precise geometry information for control purposes at every construction phase. (8)

Fig. 5. Geometry control using SOFiSTiK. (Picture: Sofin Consulting)

5.4.2 Geometry control for incremental launching

The staged construction analysis incorporated the simulation of the steel structure incremental launching employed for the approach bridges of the Kruunuvuori Bridge. This launching process posed additional challenges due to the bridge's curved plan geometry, executed by utilizing a polygonal shape for the main girders. Additionally, the last spans at the abutment featured a slight S-curve, resulting in a skewed support during the launching phase. The launch axis aligned with the plan curve, and the S-curve led to a skew support at the abutment during the launching process. Guides with a reasonable gap were employed to control the plan geometry, allowing the polygonal shape to navigate through.

Conventionally, new segments are assembled on temporary supports on the embankment behind the abutment, as an extension of the already launched bridge. The segments on the embankment are well-supported, enabling the use of non-deformed geometry. However, during the alignment of these segments, it's crucial to note that the previously installed blocks are no longer temporarily supported and, consequently, undergo deformation. In aligning these sections, it is essential to consider the deformation of the already launched part.

Fig. 6. Simulation of incremental launching. (Picture: Sofin Consulting)

During the Kruunuvuori Bridge launching, the structure exhibited a tendency to move outward from the theoretical axis within the allowable tolerance defined by the guides. The launch termination, with its small tolerance and the skew last support, inducing warping in the cross-section introduced

challenges related to the accurate positioning of the new segment on the embankment. Acknowledging these effects and tolerances, an as-built adjustment was integrated into the analysis after each launch. The realized geometry, derived from surveys, was incorporated as a new stage, activating the new segments with adjustments for the as-built geometry. Small jacking to compensate for warping due to the skew support was also included in the process. Subsequently, a new IFC model was issued for the segment assembly on the embankment. This streamlined workflow proved highly effective. The analysis, performed on the same day, facilitated the swift upload of the new IFC model to the cloud-based databank. Upon arrival, the new segments were unloaded directly to their planned position based on the IFC geometry downloaded from the cloud. The efficiency of this workflow was attributed to the absence of post-processing, as the models used for surveys were directly generated from the analysis software.

After the launch of the approach bridge spans, they are temporarily fixed in the longitudinal direction. The ultimate fixed point for the bridge is situated at the pylon. The fixing of the approach was positioned to align with its anticipated location at the time of connecting to the main bridge spans. This positioning inherently relies on temperature considerations and is determined based on the best estimate of the structure's temperature during closure. To account for uncertainties, the bridge bearings are designed with additional moving capacity to accommodate potential tolerances arising from temperature-related variations. (9)

5.5 Digital work environments and tools

Digital tools are widely used in the project. The main general 3D-model for the project includes all bridge structures, ground works, temporary structures, survey results, scanned data of the seabed and much more. One can say that all information can be found in the model. The software used for orientating the model is Trimble Connect, where even production status and percentage of completion (POC) can be visualized for each steel bridge section with colour coding of the sections.

The construction site was also photo-scanned by drone once a week, to provide real time data from the site to facilitate look-ahead planning and analyse the construction status.

6 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This paper has given the reader a brief overview of the construction process of the Crown Bridge with focus on the steel structures included in Nordec's scope. The paper has been written with the help from people who has played an essential part in the construction process starting from design to installation on site. To name a few: Nordec Oy; *Aki Viiliäinen, Tomi Vähäkangas, and Jukka Kulju*. Kreate Oy; *Ville Lehtonen, Aki Kopra, and Jari Humalajoki*. WSP Finland; *Sami Niemelä*. Ramboll Finland; *Ilkka Ojala and Eero Särkkä*. Sofin Consulting; *Atte Mikkonen*.

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